

INSTAR Roadmaps

Mapping future priority topics with our European Task Forces

11 October 2024

The European Union has long been at the forefront of global standardisation efforts, recognising that harmonised standards are crucial for enabling international trade, technological interoperability, and innovation. By collaborating with international partners, the EU aims to establish unified frameworks that ensure emerging technologies are developed and deployed in alignment with shared values, such as privacy, security, and sustainability. These joint efforts are instrumental in promoting European technological leadership, driving economic growth, and addressing global challenges through a consistent and cooperative approach to standardisation.

The recent INSTAR webinar, titled **"Mapping Future Priority Topics with our European Task Forces,"** provided a comprehensive overview of ongoing collaborative efforts to influence the trajectory of technology standardisation, with a particular emphasis on fostering international cooperation between the European Union and aligned international partner. The event featured insights from the INSTAR European Task Forces members, **Carlos Lopez Rodriguez**, representing the **European Commission DG CNECT**, and **Gianluca Misuraca**, project manager of the **Digital Partnerships in Action initiative**.

INSTAR is an EU-funded project **supporting Europe's Digital Partnerships and the EU-US TTC by collaborating with Australia, Canada, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, and the USA** to advance international standards for advanced technologies.

INSTAR'S goal is to cultivate a unified vision and **develop strategic roadmaps for ICT standards** in 5G/6G, AI, Cybersecurity/eID, Data Technologies, IoT/Edge/Cloud/Internet and Quantum Technologies, as critical enablers of future innovation.

The webinar highlighted the substantial risks associated with fragmentation within the standardisation landscape. Harmonisation of taxonomies, interoperability frameworks, and reusability of conformity assessments were identified as essential measures to mitigate such risks. Each technological domain, including AI, cybersecurity, and IoT, was examined in detail. For instance, efforts in AI are centred around fostering a shared conceptual framework through comprehensive taxonomy projects. The European experience with digital identity and trust services, particularly the eIDAS regulation, was presented as an exemplary model for promoting European standards globally, thereby demonstrating how strategic standardisation can effectively extend European influence beyond its borders.

Over **60 participants** joined the webinar from across Europe. All technology fields that INSTAR addresses were represented with participants from EU-funded projects, industrial players and SDOs.

A good number of members of INSTAR's European Task Forces joined the webinar,

Roadmaps: Mapping future priority topics with our ETFs
11 OCTOBER 2024 | 11:00-12:00 (CEST)

Event Takeaways:

The EU, through its Digital Partnerships, focuses on creating tangible, actionable solutions for global standardisation. The "Brussels effect" plays a crucial role in this, where EU regulations influence global markets. When the EU introduces new regulations, companies around the world must align with them to access the European market. This results in the global adoption of EU regulations and standards.

The EU has prioritised the "Digital Product Passport" and "Digital Identity Wallet." The eIDAS 2 regulation builds on previous frameworks, aiming to simplify digital identity management with a user-friendly Digital Wallet.

Ensuring that AI applications can communicate effectively with IoT devices is a significant challenge. This requires horizontal interoperability. Achieving seamless interoperability of concepts and architectures is essential for progress in these areas.

The EU supports its policy implementation by contributing to training and capacity building with international partners, and ensuring conformity with standards like the GDPR, AI Act, and Cyber Resilience Act.

Insights from the experts:

"One of the main pillars of the European Standardisation Strategy is to try to promote European leadership in global standardisation and digital technologies."

Carlos Lopez Rodriguez - EC DG CNECT Policy Officer, ICT Standardisation Sector

"Cybersecurity is no longer an option but a necessity. Today, more than one billion people worldwide are without a recognised identity, which means no access to medical records, property rights, or education. These are not just technical issues; they are fundamentally about societal well-being."

Paolo Campegiani - Cybersecurity/eID ETF expert

"The biggest challenge we face is integration—bringing together IoT, data spaces, and AI into cohesive ecosystems. The concept of a 'digital twin' is becoming crucial in this space, providing a powerful abstraction for everyone, from managers to engineers, to understand and operationalise this integration."

Antonio Kung - Trialog Co-Founder

"Fragmentation is our main weakness. We do not yet have a common European approach, and this is why initiatives like INSTAR and DPA are crucial – fostering better coordination and cooperation across EU activities."

Gianluca Misuraca - Digital Partnerships in Action Project Coordinator

Watch the recording!
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